

ISic4350

I.Sicily inscription 4350

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2016.05.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

exact provenance unknown, "Siracusa" written in black ink on the
reverse

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo di Archeologia
dell'Universita di Catania, inventory 05/145

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G. 2014. Iscrizioni. In Biondi, G., Buscemi Felici, G., Tortorici, E.(eds.), *Il museo archeologico dell'Università di Catania. Collezione Libertini*. Acireale. pp. 170-173. At 171 no.239 fig.41

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